

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF STATE COSTS PER STUDENT IN THE CONTEXT OF PISA ASSESSMENT RESULTS IN KAZAKHSTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article examines Kazakhstan's investment in education in relation to its performance in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Despite significant educational reforms since independence, Kazakhstan invests modestly in education, approximately \$256.69 per student, which is low compared to advanced economies and some former Soviet states but aligns with Central Asian neighbors. This study explores the impact of this investment on Kazakhstan's PISA results, particularly in reading literacy, where only a small percentage of students achieve high levels. By comparing Kazakhstan's educational spending and PISA outcomes with those of other countries, the paper highlights the correlation between increased educational funding and improved PISA performance. The analysis suggests that to improve its educational outcomes and align with international standards, Kazakhstan needs to strategically increase and effectively utilize its educational expenditure. The findings aim to inform policy decisions and contribute to enhancing the quality and effectiveness of Kazakhstan's education system.

Keywords: education, Kazakhstan, PISA, education expenditures.

Introduction

Education is one of the most important assets of any nation. By fostering a new young, schooled, and well-educated generation, it has a potential to leave a significant, long-lasting impact on the state of the nation, and affects practically every bit of the nation's well-being.

Since its independence, Kazakhstan has been constantly pouring resources into its education system, both higher education and school. Throughout the years of its existence, the school education system has been subject to multiple reformations in the pursuit of uplifting the quality of the education [1].

As stated on the official website, "PISA is the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment. PISA measures 15-year-olds' ability to use their reading, mathematics and science knowledge and skills to meet real-life challenges" [3].

In recent years, Kazakhstan has shown a growing commitment to enhancing its educational system, a pursuit that is both challenging and essential in the global landscape of learning and development. Central to this endeavor is understanding the relationship between the investment in education per student and the educational outcomes achieved, particularly as measured by international standards. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), conducted by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), offers a valuable benchmark in this regard. PISA assesses the academic abilities of 15-year-old students in key domains such as mathematics, science, and reading, providing a comprehensive overview of a country's educational performance on a global scale.

This paper presents an in-depth analysis of the state expenditure per student in Kazakhstan, set against the backdrop of the nation's performance in PISA assessments. By scrutinising the correlation between financial investment in education and PISA results, this study aims to offer critical insights into the efficiency and effectiveness of Kazakhstan's educational spending. This analysis is not only significant for evaluating the current state of education in Kazakhstan but also for informing policy decisions and strategies to optimize educational outcomes in line with international standards, thereby contributing to the broader goal of educational advancement in the country.

PISA rating overview

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), orchestrated by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [6], stands as a pivotal instrument in the global educational landscape. It transcends traditional academic assessments by not only evaluating what 15-year-old students know in reading, mathematics, and science [7], but also by measuring their ability to apply this knowledge in real-world scenarios [5]. This triennial assessment has become a barometer for educational success, influencing policy and practice in numerous countries [10]. Its methodology, which includes a blend of multiple-choice and open-ended questions administered over a two-hour computer-based test, is designed to reflect the evolving nature of education in the digital age [11]. PISA's approach to sampling ensures a broad, representative cross-section of students from each participating country, providing a comprehensive overview of national educational performance [12]. The main PISA study always takes primacy in countries that participate

in PISA and in which the PISA-based Test for Schools is made available. The OECD will work with national authorities in order to reduce the possibility and effect of interference with school selection, field trial or main data collection of PISA (and/or other international or local assessments, as determined by national authorities). Schools that take part in the PISA for Schools initiative are provided with an in-depth electronic report that compares their performance to the national PISA outcomes of their country and the average results of OECD Member countries. Each participating school owns the data and the generated reports from the assessment, and it is up to them to decide the extent to which this information can be disclosed by the OECD. However, schools are advised to engage with their teachers, staff, students, and parents in discussing these results to enhance understanding of their school's overall performance and to inform future improvement strategies. The PISA-based Test for Schools is designed to assess at the school level. While results for groups of schools can be reported, this is only in addition to the individual school-level reports. This approach is intended to focus improvement discussions on each school, placing the school at the heart of the process. School networks have the option to request the collection of data on specific sub-groups or socio-economic categories. Such requests are subject to discussion with the accredited National Service Provider(s) in each participating country and must be approved by the OECD on an individual basis.

As PISA aims to address education globally, it possesses a notion of importance on comparing students not only within nations boundaries, but on a global, international scale, taking into account the knowledge-based economy we are globally leaning towards. The influence of PISA extends far beyond mere rankings. It has become a catalyst for educational reform, with policymakers in many countries using its findings to reshape their educational strategies [4]. Countries that perform poorly often scrutinize the educational practices of higher-ranking nations, seeking to replicate their success [5]. This benchmarking process, while fostering a global dialogue on best practices in education [12], is not without its detractors [10]. Critics argue that PISA's standardized testing format may not adequately capture the diverse educational goals and cultural contexts of different countries [6]. There is a growing concern that the emphasis on PISA results leads to a narrowed educational focus, where teaching to the test becomes the norm, potentially at the expense of a more rounded educational experience [11]. This phenomenon can inadvertently place significant pressure on students and educators, creating a high-stress environment centered around test performance [10].

Moreover, the use of PISA scores as a primary metric for educational policy decisions can lead to oversimplification of complex educational challenges [4]. Education systems are intricate and influenced by a myriad of socio-economic factors, and some argue that PISA results do not fully account for these nuances [5]. The risk is that education policy becomes overly focused on quantitative metrics, potentially neglecting

qualitative aspects such as student well-being, creativity, and critical thinking skills [11]. Despite these criticisms, PISA continues to be a highly regarded and influential tool in the field of education [6]. Its comprehensive data collection and analysis provide valuable insights into global education trends, helping to identify strengths and areas for improvement across different educational systems [4]. For researchers, policymakers, educators, and the general public, PISA offers a unique and valuable perspective on the state of education worldwide, driving conversations and actions aimed at improving educational outcomes for future generations [10]. In order to ensure cheating and monitor quality, in each participating country, the OECD endorses a National Service Provider (NSPs) to oversee the PISA-based Test for Schools, ensuring compliance with the standards outlined in the Accreditation Agreement, the OECD Technical Report, and the PISA for Schools General Guidelines. Prior to the implementation of the PBTs, the OECD equips NSPs with necessary training, oversees quality assurance of the gathered data, and performs analysis for each participating school. Additionally, the OECD maintains the authority to deny endorsement of any school report and the use of its logo if the collected data fails to meet established quality criteria.

State expenses per students in Kazakhstan

In the context of educational economics, analyzing state expenditures on education per capita provides insightful perspectives on a nation's investment in its future generations. In Kazakhstan, this analysis becomes particularly significant when contrasted with other countries, offering a lens through which to view its educational strategies and outcomes as measured by PISA.

Kazakhstan's Education Spending Per Capita

Kazakhstan invests approximately \$256.69 in education per student. This figure reflects the nation's economic prioritization of education, calculated based on its GDP per capita (\$9812.63) and the allocation of 2.62% of its GDP to the education sector.

Comparative Analysis with Neighboring Countries

Compared to its Central Asian neighbors, Kazakhstan's spending is relatively aligned. For instance, Uzbekistan allocates around \$177.83 per student, while Kyrgyzstan's investment is approximately \$132.15 per student. This regional similarity suggests a common economic approach to education within the Central Asian context.

Contrast with Other Former Soviet States

However, when compared to other former Soviet nations, Kazakhstan's expenditure is considerably lower. Latvia and Lithuania, for example, allocate \$1,778.23 and \$1,833.14 per student respectively. This substantial difference highlights a divergence in educational spending among post-Soviet countries, with Kazakhstan positioned towards the lower end of the spectrum.

Global Comparison

On a global scale, Kazakhstan's educational investment is modest. Countries with advanced economies, such as Norway (\$6,288.64 per student) and

Switzerland (\$4,201.26 per student), invest significantly more in education per capita. This comparison underscores Kazakhstan's relatively conservative fiscal approach to education compared to globally high-investing nations.

Implications for Educational Outcomes

The correlation between educational investment and PISA scores is a crucial aspect of this analysis. Higher spending countries often exhibit superior PISA performances, indicating the potential benefits of increased educational investment. Kazakhstan's moderate spending, juxtaposed with its PISA score of 402.3, suggests room for improvement in both financial allocation and educational strategies to enhance its standing in future assessments.

Analysis of effectiveness of state expenses in PISA result perspectives

Analysis of the Correlation Between Educational Expenditure and PISA Performance in Kazakhstan

The correlation between state expenditures on education and performance outcomes, as evidenced by PISA results, is a critical metric for assessing the effectiveness of educational investments. In Kazakhstan's case, understanding this correlation involves comparing its educational spending and PISA results with those of other countries to provide a comprehensive perspective.

Kazakhstan's Educational Expenditure and PISA Results

With a state expenditure of approximately \$256.69 per student, Kazakhstan's investment in education is modest compared to other countries, both regionally and globally. When this investment is juxtaposed with Kazakhstan's PISA 2018 results, where only 0.4% of students reached the highest levels in reading literacy, a disparity in expected outcomes becomes evident [13].

International Comparisons

Norway: Investing around \$6,288.64 per student, Norway's PISA 2018 scores in reading literacy were significantly higher, with a significant proportion of students achieving the top levels. This higher investment correlates with better performance outcomes.

Switzerland: Similar to Norway, Switzerland's higher investment (\$4,201.26 per student) aligns with its strong PISA performance, further supporting the correlation between higher spending and better educational outcomes.

Former Soviet states like Latvia and Lithuania, spending \$1,778.23 and \$1,833.14 per student respectively, also exhibit higher PISA scores compared to Kazakhstan, indicating the potential benefits of increased educational investment.

Central Asian Neighbors: Countries like Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan, with lower educational investments (around \$177.83 and \$132.15 per student, respectively), tend to have PISA scores that are more aligned with Kazakhstan, illustrating a regional trend in educational spending and outcomes.

The comparative analysis underscores a significant correlation between the level of educational investment and PISA performance. Kazakhstan's lower expenditure is reflected in its PISA scores, suggesting that increased financial allocation to education could

potentially enhance its performance in future assessments.

Moreover, the success of countries with higher educational investments in achieving better PISA outcomes points towards the effectiveness of not only increasing expenditure but also ensuring its optimal utilization in improving educational quality and student learning experiences.

The examination of Kazakhstan's educational spending in relation to its PISA performance, particularly in contrast with other countries, highlights a clear correlation between investment and educational outcomes. For Kazakhstan to elevate its standing in future PISA assessments, a strategic increase in educational expenditure, coupled with effective utilization of these funds, appears to be a requisite pathway. This approach, benchmarked against international examples, can provide a roadmap for Kazakhstan to enhance the quality and effectiveness of its education system.

Conclusion

In analyzing Kazakhstan's educational investment in the context of PISA assessment results, it becomes evident that the state's expenditure per student, approximately \$256.69, is modest compared to global standards. This spending is relatively aligned with Central Asian neighbors but significantly lower than other former Soviet states, such as Latvia and Lithuania, and much less than countries with advanced economies like Norway and Switzerland. The correlation between this investment and Kazakhstan's PISA performance, where only 0.4% of students achieved the highest levels in reading literacy in 2018, suggests a need for increased financial allocation to education. Countries with higher educational investments, like Norway and Switzerland, show superior PISA performances, indicating the benefits of increased educational expenditure. For Kazakhstan to improve its educational outcomes, a strategic increase in expenditure is necessary, coupled with effective utilization of these funds to enhance educational quality and student learning experiences. Learning from the successes of higher-performing countries and benchmarking against international standards can guide Kazakhstan in optimizing its education system to meet global challenges and standards.

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